

Climate Crisis and Women Health: A Case Study of India

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Abstract

On a worldwide scale, the climate catastrophe is a great struggle. The impacts on the ecosystem, income, trade, health, and security of persons in different facets of the economy are extensive. Climate instability contributes to elevated temperatures, natural disasters, diseases, water scarcity, erratic monsoons, ocean acidification, and forest fires. This paper examines the effects of the climate crisis on women's health to comprehend the economic and social structure of their daily lives as a consequence of disasters, along with presenting a theoretical framework with the target of understanding the burden placed on girls to drop out of their education and assist their parents with chores at home. Climate change poses a threat to safe drinking water, health and hygiene, mental disorders, psychological distress, illnesses that impacts the mother's health, pregnancy through transmitted diseases, and growing exposure to heat waves, sick building syndrome, and food insecurity with an unbalanced diet leading to undernourishment. The study is conducted using secondary data from different sources like World Bank, The United Nations Framework and Convention on Climate Change, World Health Organization (WHO), World Meteorological Organization, and The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). This research paper attempts to analyze that during adverse situations such as droughts, floods, and pandemics, women are anticipated to change their focus of energy towards the home and family duties, providing them with a lesser amount of time for studying, generating a livelihood, training, and education. Climate change causes hardship and suffering for families, especially in the countryside, wherein women suffer more than men. The result of the same could be observed on their unemployment rates. They become perpetrators of sexual and domestic assault, confront gender disparities, lack the capacity for decision-making and differentiated powers, have limited mobility through states, and are vulnerable, impacting their physical, emotional, and mental health.

Keywords Economy, Health, Climate Change, Impacts, Unemployment, Rural Area.

Introduction

According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), climate change has had a substantial influence on women and will have negative implications. This is especially true in the case of health issues. In India, 47 million women were impoverished, compared to 39 million men. (Sanyukta Kanwal, 2021). Given the situation of inequalities and gender-based discrimination, women's vulnerabilities are exacerbated. The climate catastrophe, like any other disaster, pandemic, or economic insecurity, has a greater impact on women than men owing to unequal power distribution, gender disparity in education, work possibilities, violence, and unequal salary compensation. (UNEP, 2023) In terms of medical accessibility, women are frequently denied treatment or clinicians do not address the specific ailment from which they are suffering. Women are hesitant to speak with doctors about their health concerns, which involve predominantly men, and their situation is frequently overlooked in rural India. They are frequently engaged in domestic responsibilities, her future possibilities are restricted to early marriage. Women in India, particularly in rural regions, sometimes suffer in silence, denied access to decent education: often, their male brothers are educated in spite of women. Parents invest more money in their son's education. They are barred from decision-making, thus their function is limited to cooking and home tasks, taking care of everyone else's needs while forgetting about their own, and suffering in silence inside four walls. A study released on International Women's Day demonstrates the nutritional well-being of

adolescent girls and women of childbearing age. Research shows that nearly a billion women are undernourished or have vitamin and mineral deficiencies. (UNICEF, 2023). Prolonged heat exposure intensifies its biological impacts on the human body. In the case of women, it leads to stillbirth, and complications during pregnancy, and younger mothers have more powerful and more severe repercussions. In this study, we will focus on women's health and how it relates to food insecurity as a result of the climate catastrophe in the country of India.

Aim of study

The aim of this paper is to provide an outline of the advancement of climate change and the subject matter in broad. The intent of the writing is to study the impact of the climate crisis on women's health in the context of India and review the government's policy involvement to combat climate disasters.

Review of Literature

Charlotta Rylander, Jon Oyvind Odland' and Torkjel Manning Sandanger (2013) the study was conducted for improved comprehension of the potential impacts of the climate crisis on women's reproductive health, pregnancy results, and newborns. The study connects the findings to the Millennium Development Goals and the Sustainable Development Goals. According to the study, poor maternal health conditions are responsible for around 3 million infant deaths and stillbirths each year. During a climatic crisis, women are deprived of nourishment as well as are confronted by infectious diseases due to a poor living environment when it comes to cleanliness, sanitation, and water scarcity.

Cecillia Sorensen (2018) the following study was carried to better comprehend the implications of the Climate Crisis on women's health. The study identified substantial factors such as poor air quality, heat exposure, food insecurity, reproductive difficulties in pregnancy, and premature deliveries. Given their societal, cultural, economic, and biological differences, men and women are influenced differently. The study went on to address policy interventions and approaches to reduce climate and catastrophe risk.

Arsheem Qasim (2019) the author concentrated on how the climate disastrous events impact women in their everyday lives. The study cites five factors, which are as follows: a higher risk of violence against women and girls, increased probability of child marriage, they are additionally more likely to drop out of school, an elevated risk of mortality and disease, which impacts their work position and jeopardizes their food security. In rural areas, men are frequently the primary breadwinner and rule their spouses. Furthermore, in the event of a calamity, they typically depart from their family or go to cities to earn a living, leaving their families behind at home.

Chitrita Sengupta Chaki (2022) the author attempted to investigate the impact of the Climate Crisis on women's mental health rather than biological variables. Women make up sixty-five percent of the agricultural workforce; nevertheless, they are less likely to get help and knowledge on how to address the situation, making them more prone and susceptible. Numerous shreds of evidence were presented in the study from Uganda, Haiti, and Nepal that demonstrated that climatic catastrophes increased cases of child marriage and financial difficulties, which exacerbated domestic violence.

Mrittika Mallick (2022) the objective of this research is to collect information regarding the barriers that women experience while dealing with a climate crisis. They suffer from miscarriages, yeast infections, and UTIs (Urinary Tract Infections) as a result of shifting temperatures, particularly those who live near the sea or rivers. Climate change also has an impact on food security, which negatively impacts adolescent dietary patterns, causing excessive bleeding and menstrual cycles to begin earlier than usual.

Sonja A. Rasmussen and Denise J. Jamieson (2022) the study focuses on climate change and the hazards it poses to human life, particularly women's health, and newborns. The study indicates a variety of negative consequences underlying the climate crisis, such as wildfires. The author explained how smoke exposes pregnant women to toxic fumes, volatile chemicals, and particulate matter, as well as increasing the risk of gestational hypertension and gestational diabetes during pregnancy. Due to disaster, families frequently travel to other regions in search of a safe place to live, interrupting pregnant women's access to health care and medications, a dynamic atmosphere, deprived of social support, which can have long-term consequences.

Taylor Morris (2022) the research project was undertaken to discover the influence of climate change on women's health in the context of pregnancy, and the numerous reasons surrounding that are concerned. Air pollution and severe temperatures are two of them that have elevated the likelihood of lung malfunction and induced the development of asthma in young ones. According to the research findings, exceptionally high temperatures have resulted in stillbirth, premature birth, and low birth weight.

Main Text

India's Exposure to Climate Crisis and Gender Disparity

Climate change has historically been experienced in various scenarios such as droughts, storms, rising temperatures creating heat exposure, excessive rain that causes flooding, cyclones, air and water

contamination which ended in toxic gases along with other volatile substances, water scarcity, and several more.

Women have suffered more as a result of climate change than men since they rely on their husbands for living and basic requirements. During a crisis, men are frequently observed migrating to other cities in search of work, whilst women are tied to home chores. With less education, they tend to have low-paying occupations with no security and lack knowledge of how to deal with dreadful scenarios. In India, the majority of women are active in agricultural operations, yet females have far less access to raw resources than men and no participation in decision-making, contributing to gender inequality. Food supply is severely impeded by heavy monsoons or droughts, and most women are observed prioritizing their husband's health and neglecting their own, resulting in malnutrition and several other harmful impacts on their health.

Effect of Rising Temperatures and Contamination of Air on Women's Maternal Health

Excessive heat in pregnant women can lead to complications such as stillbirth, early delivery, and low birth weight. Air pollution also causes lung disorders and has a genetic influence. Asthma can affect both pregnant mothers and their newborns. Maternal health is critical to the success of a healthy delivery result.

Figure. 1 Impact of Heat Exposure on Health

Source: World Health Organization, 2018

The population which is most vulnerable to heat is the elderly, kids and newborns, pregnant women, outdoor and manual laborers, sportspeople, and the underprivileged. Gender can have a significant impact on heat exposure.

Infectious Illness Transmission is aided by Climate Change

Malaria is a life-threatening disease caused by parasites that are transmitted to people through the bites of infected female Anopheles mosquitoes. (World Health Organization) India represented 83% of projected cases and approximately 82% of all malaria fatalities in 2020. As per NFHS-5, about 57 percent of women in India are anemic. Due to the increased risk of preterm, intrauterine development restriction, and low birth weight, a substantial percentage of newborns delivered to malaria-infected pregnant mothers in India are likely to suffer from severe health impairments. These, furthermore, can become major predictors for numerous chronic illnesses (e.g., diabetes, nutritional concerns) in adults. Childhood exposure to malaria is additionally believed to be an important contributor to low intellect in infected neonates, with long-term deleterious effects on academic achievement.

Figure 2: Prevalence of Malaria in Pregnancy in India